

WORKSHOP FACILITATION CARDS: Instructions for DIY Sticker Printing

1. PRINTING

The PDF file you've downloaded was designed and formatted specifically to print at 100% scale on A4-sized paper.

The best brand of sticker paper that we have tested at the Arctic Centre is called "Talex," but many others should work. It may be worth testing with a few different types for the best results; some brands experienced problems while printing, like sheets sticking together from static or ink smearing too easily from the surface. Very importantly, the paper should be one whole sticker sheet that is not pre-cut or pre-divided into smaller labels. The paper loaded into your printer should have the following features:

Type: Self-Adhesive/Sticker Paper for inkjet or laser printers

Size: A4 (210×297mm)

Finish: White, Matte

When a dialogue box pops up on your screen, please pay special attention to these print settings:

- *Full color*
- *Single-sided*
- *Paper size A4*
- *Scale: 100%*

Printer: HP OfficeJet Pro 9010 series

Presets: Default Settings

Copies: 1 Black & White Two-Sided

Pages: All
 Selected Page in Sidebar
 From: 1 to: 1

Paper Size: A4 3.27 by 11.69 inches

Orientation: Portrait Landscape

Preview

Auto Rotate Show Notes

Scale: 100%

Scale to Fit: Print Entire Image Fill Entire Paper

Copies per page: 1

PDF

2. CUTTING

The best way to cut out the stickers in a neat and efficient way is to use a straight-edge (e.g. ruler) and a blade (e.g. scalpel, box cutter). It's very important that the blade is sharp so that the paper does not snag or tear.

You'll see crop marks all along the edge of the printed cards. They are the small black lines indicating where you'll be lining up your straight edge.

Start with the 6 shorter cuts, which run width-wise along the paper. It's important not to cut all the way from edge to edge of the paper; simply start cutting at one crop mark and lift the blade after you reach the next crop mark. Your first set of cuts should look like these lines:

Next make the 3 longer cuts, which run lengthwise along the paper. It's important to start cutting from the right edge, pressing the straight-edge tightly to the left of the blade. This way, the strips of paper will stay in place as you begin to cut pieces loose. Your second set of cuts should look like these lines:

Continue in this manner until each A4-sized sheet has yielded 10 identically sized rectangles.

3. ADHERING

Some brands of sticker paper may have a natural peel-off line that runs through the A4 sheet. However, this may not run through each of the stickers you have just cut to size. In cases where there is no intersecting peel-off line, peel gently starting from a corner of the rectangle until the sticker separates from its backing. Try not to fold the front side of the sticker while peeling away the backing, as it may create a visible crease on the printed ink border.

Using any standard deck of playing cards, begin to adhere the stickers. For consistent placement, try to line up two or three of the corners against the border of a playing card before applying pressure. Press down slowly, smoothing out the sticker from one end to another (this will decrease the likelihood of trapping air bubbles or creating creases). The dimensions of these stickers have been designed to fit on any deck of playing cards, despite variations in length/width measurements. It's okay for some of the underlying card design to show through or peek around the edges of the sticker, as long as the words are legible!

